

Exciplex revisited†

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I feel honoured for being called upon to deliver this lecture in memory of Acharya J. C. Ghosh who initiated researches on basic physical chemistry in India. He has been acclaimed for his performance as planner and builder of Indian technology in post-independent era, for the 'spell-bound' quality of his classroom lectures, and for his pioneering research contributions to electrochemistry, photochemistry and high-pressure chemistry. It is a matter of great regret that the present generation of chemistry students are unaware of his contribution to the calculation of ionic Free Energy. His contribution preceded that of Debye and Hückel by several years and was referred to as 'Ghosh's Theory' by eminent scientists like Donnan, Bragg, Nernst, Planck and Lewis¹. It is gratifying to note that his lattice model has been dug out of the grave in recent times by some electrochemists who has applied it to the case of highly concentrated solutions. The Indian Chemical Society should take some corrective measures to put his theory in proper perspective in text-books of physical chemistry.

Relatively less known is his contributions to photochemistry and kinetics of chemical reactions, a topic which he initiated at the Dhaka University (1922-39). Here also, in sharp contrast to the current lure for soft problems and long publication lists, he explored important, novel and difficult problems, such as, mechanism of catalysis of redox reactions by chlorophyll molecule, production of enantiomorphic excess by circularly polarized light etc. He designed and built his own setup with indigenous materials and locally available talents² – a culture that has almost vanished from our laboratories now-a-days.

In order to explain the photophysics of chlorophyll-catalysed redox reactions, Ghosh suggested complex formation in the photo-excited state between chlorophyll and one of the reaction partners before the transfer of electron from (or to) the chlorophyll molecule². One can identify the seed of the present-day concept of exciplex in this suggestion. After Mulliken introduced the concept of charge-transfer (C-T) band and bond in 1952, Professor Sadhan Basu, another illustrious physical chemist of our country, tried hard to identify the C-T complex in the excited state. He found a correlation between the intensity of fluorescence of pyrene and the ionisation potential of the solvent³. The first definite evidence of an excited state C-T complex was, however, obtained by Leonhardt and Weller in 1963

when they observed a broad long-wavelength emission band from a mixture of pyrene and dimethylaniline⁴. This band was highly sensitive to the dielectric constant ϵ of the medium, indicating clearly the polar nature of the emitting species, which was named as exciplex. The dipole moment of the exciplex was determined from the ϵ dependence of ν_{\max} using Lippert-Mataga equation⁵, which corresponded to a nearly complete transfer of one electron from one partner to another. Subsequent to the discovery of exciplex, volumes of work have been carried out on both emitting and non-emitting exciplexes⁶. These are frequently intermediates in photoelectron transfer reactions some of which have even been exploited even for storing light energy. It is worth noting that the quantum yield of photo-products is determined not only by the rate of the forward electron transfer, but also by the rate of the back electron transfer (BET). In chlorophyll-mediated photosynthesis the BET is reduced by transfer of the electron accepted by the first acceptor to a second acceptor. Another means of controlling the BET could be, in principle, spin-control of the two radicals generated by electron transfer in an exciplex. If the spin orientations of the two newly generated radicals are turned parallel, the recombination or BET could be largely prevented. This aspect of exciplex-born geminate radical pair (RP) or radical ion pair (RIP) recombination has drawn the attention of scientists in the last two decades⁷. This will be the main theme of our discussion.

The potential energy surface (PES) relevant for an exciplex is shown in Fig. 1^{6f,7}. The ground state PES is repul-

Fig. 1. A schematic diagram of exciplex system both in polar and non-polar mediums.

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sive in nature : the same should be true for the PES corresponding to $(A^*,D)^{6f,7}$ in the zeroth order. These non-ionic PESs are hardly affected by the solvent dielectric constant. On the other hand, the PESs corresponding to a RIP are solvent- ϵ sensitive. In low ϵ medium, and at an infinite distance the energy of D^+A^- is in most cases higher than that of DA^* . At shorter distances Coulombic attraction lowers the energy of an ionic configuration considerably and there is a strong first order configuration interaction between non-CT and CT states. As a consequence of this interaction, the D^*A PES has a minimum at a short intermolecular distance, which allows formation of a complex. In addition, due to mixing between D^*A and D^+A^- the exciplex formed at this minimum develops polar character. In a high- ϵ medium, both D^+ and A^- are solvated and therefore, at infinite separation ionic configuration has energy lower than the D^*A . At short distances, further energy lowering of the D^+A^- is much smaller; in other words, compared to that in non-polar media the Coulombic cage is shallow in the polar medium. There, however, are two minima : one corresponds to solvent-shared radical ion pair (SSRIP) and the other to contact ion pair (CIP). There is a barrier between the SSRIP minimum and the CIP minimum, for energy is required to squeeze out the shared solvent molecules of the SSRIP. While the above two-minima description is correct for the singlet state of the RIP, the same is not true for the repulsive triplet state. Triplet and singlet curves of SSRIP merge beyond an intermolecular distance of ~ 10 Å when the exchange intergral becomes negligible. Even if the triplet curve has a Coulombic minimum, it is at a much greater distance than the singlet 'SSRIP' minimum.

On excitation of the acceptor, the D,A^* drops to the lower energy surface D^+A^- by electron transfer. The exact distance where this electron transfer occurs is not known in polar media. It could vary from the CIP distance (~ 4 Å) to distances of the order of 15 Å or even greater. In any case, the donor or the acceptor of the RIP undergoes diffusional excursion inward and outward on the PES. When it drops radiatively to the ground state from CIP, the exciplex fluoresces. If it drops to the ground PES at larger distances by BET, no radiation emerges. Still another alternative open for the pair is to cross over to the triplet surface and then drop to the lower energy (3A,D) PES. The latter process though spin-forbidden, can take place if the singlet and the triplet are of the same energy and if there is some other simultaneous process which could compensate for the electron-spin-angular momentum change^{6f,7}. This intersystem crossing (ISC) aspect in a RP is focused in the next paragraph.

The spin-angular momentum change in a $S \rightarrow T$ transition needs to be compensated. This may be achieved by any one of the following processes : (a) Orbital angular momentum change, (b) Rotational angular momentum change, (c) Nuclear spin angular momentum change and (d) Change in angular momentum in the magnetic field

coil. The first two are not very important for a light-atom radical pair in condensed phase. Both internal nuclear magnetic field (i.e. mechanism c) and external field (i.e. mechanism d) have been shown to be significant for ISC in RP. An external field causes the two decoupled electrons (i.e. $J = 0$) on the two radicals to precess round the field axis Z at frequencies given by $\omega_1 = g_1\beta H$. If g_1 is different from g_2 , the relative phase of the two electrons could change from the singlet to the triplet configuration causing a $S \leftrightarrow T_0$ transition. This is shown in Fig. 2(a). Note that a

Fig. 2. A diagrammatic representation of singlet to triplet spin evolution within a radical pair. Fig. (a) shows that $S \leftrightarrow T_0$ spin evolution takes place by the interaction of externally applied magnetic field and the component of total spin in the direction of magnetic field and/or by the interaction of the component of nuclear moment and the component of spin moment in the Z -direction, whereas, $S \leftrightarrow T_{\pm 1}$ spin evolution takes place by the interaction of the components of nuclear and spin moments which are perpendicular to the Z -axis. Fig. (b) shows how increasing Zeeman interaction (ZI) (i.e. increasing magnetic field) suppresses the $S \leftrightarrow T$ evolution by gradually blocking the $S \leftrightarrow T_{\pm 1}$ channels

$S \rightarrow T_{\pm 1}$ transition is not possible by an external laboratory field. Similarly, the electron spin vector precesses round a resultant vector obtained by coupling the electron spin angular momentum with the spin angular momentum of nuclei attached to that radical. There is, however, one difference between the internal field case and the external field case. Since the nuclear angular momentum could have components in any of the three laboratory directions, the precession has components along the three laboratory axes. As a consequence, all the three transitions $S \rightarrow T_0, T_{\pm 1}$ could occur by this coupling with the internal nuclear magnetic field.

The next question that arises is – what will happen if both internal and external fields are present? In absence of the magnetic field, all the three channels $S \rightarrow T_{0,\pm 1}$ are

open. In presence of a field which splits the $T_{\pm 1}$ levels to an extent exceeding the hyperfine width of levels, two of the channels $S \rightarrow T_{\pm 1}$ are blocked while the third channel remains open (Fig. 2b). Thus, at a very low field the Zeeman interaction exceeds the hyperfine width of levels and the MFE saturates out if the field is further increased. This coupled spin-cum-spatial-evolution model of the RIP is able to explain most of the observations on MFE on exciplex luminescence which we are going to discuss next^{6f,7}.

Variation of MFE with field

Except at very low fields, the exciplex luminescence intensity increases almost linearly with field, upto a field of the order of 100G and then saturates out at a field of about 200 gauss (Fig. 3)⁸. This behaviour is a clear signature of hyperfine mechanism which has been elucidated in the pre-

Fig. 3. A plot of the variation of $\Delta\phi/\phi$ with applied magnetic field strength. INDO-HUF calculation shows that for pyrene-DMA system the calculated $B_{1/2}$ is 56G which is almost the same as the experimental value; whereas, for ANTH-PFN system the $B_{1/2}$ value depends on the distortion of the fluorine atoms of PFN molecule; for 0° , 10° and 20° distortions the $B_{1/2}$ values are 21, 43 and 96G respectively.

vious section. The field at which the MFE attains half the saturation value is called $B_{1/2}$, which is related to the average hyperfine interaction in the two radicals. Theoretical calculation of hyperfine interaction in general, is in good agreement with the observed value of $B_{1/2}$, barring a few exceptions. One of the exceptions is the system octafluoronaphthalene-pyrene recently studied by us⁹. A fairly large $B_{1/2}$ (≈ 130 gauss) has been observed. Theoretical calculation on planar OFN, however, predicts a low value. The gap between the calculated value and the observed value may be bridged considerably if the molecule is assumed floppy in the excited state⁹.

At very low fields, the exciplex luminescence intensity is rather insensitive to field. In some cases, particularly in systems where the donor and the acceptor are linked by short flexible chains, an opposite trend is observed; namely, the exciplex luminescence intensity decreases with increase of field¹⁰. This has been ascribed to a non-zero J value when the separation between the donor and the acceptor is small. At zero field, there exists (for small separations between radical partners) a gap between S and $T_{0,\pm 1}$.

With application of field, one of the two split $T_{\pm 1}$ states become degenerate with the singlet state, and thus the $S \rightarrow T_{+1}$ (or T_{-1}) transition rate is increased causing a decrease in exciplex luminescence intensity.

Magnitude of MFE and its variation with solvent properties^{6f,7,11,12}

The magnitude of MFE for the Py/DMA system in alcoholic solvents is small, the maximum being about 2% in methanol/ethanol solvent mixture corresponding to a $\epsilon \approx 26$. The magnitude however increases considerably if aprotic solvents are used and the dielectric constant is adjusted to about 16. For example, in thoroughly dried THF/DMF mixtures we have recently recorded a MFE^{\max} of 13.5%^{11d}. A still higher MFE^{\max} of 20% has now been reported by Petrov *et al.* in dried DMSO/toluene mixture^{12c}. Three characteristics of the solvent mixture are supposed to be important in determining the magnitude of

Fig. 4. Variation of magnetic field modulated exciplex luminescence, $[\Delta\phi/\phi]$, with dielectric constant in several binary solvent mixtures.

MFE. (a) First, the dielectric constant of the medium considerably modifies the PES on which the two ionic radicals wander about. At very low ϵ , the two ionic radicals are close to each other and the non-zero J (exchange integral) inhibits ISC crossing. At very high ϵ , the fraction of geminate recombination is less; this again leads to a low MFE. The MFE, therefore, peaks at an intermediate dielectric constant (Fig. 4). Normally the peak in MFE oc-

Fig. 5. Variation of the ratio of magnetic field induced change in exciplex luminescence intensity to exciplex luminescence intensity in absence of magnetic field, $[\Delta\phi/\phi]$, of pyrene-DMA system at 520 nm.

Fig. 6. (a) The MFE quenching capability of different Ln^{3+} ions. (The deGennes factor (G) is equal to $(g-1)(J+1)$). (b) The rotation of the spin vector of one of the radicals due to coupling with the spin moment of the lanthanide ion.

curs at about $\epsilon \approx 16$ in aprotic solvents. Recently cases of peaks at ϵ lower than 16 have also been reported^{11c}. (2) Second, the microheterogeneity of the medium has also been suggested to play a role¹². In case of flash-photolytic studies of radical pairs, it has been unambiguously shown that micelles enhance MFE. The micellar boundary acts as a reflector of the separating radicals and thereby increases the percentage of geminate recombination and hence the overall MFE. Petrov *et al.* also observed that exciplex luminescence shows considerably higher MFE^{max} in mixtures of non-polar benzene and polar DMSO¹². They suggested that the ion is preferentially solvated by the polar component causing a trough in the potential energy sur-

face, which accelerates or retards geminate recombination after the required spin evolution. We tested this concept by taking water/dioxane and water/THF medium, and surprisingly could not get any evidence of microheterogeneity aiding the MFE^{11c} . We found that the nature of the non-polar component of the solvent mixture, and not just the polar component, has considerable influence on the MFE (Fig. 5). (3) The third feature of the solvent which influences considerably the magnitude of MFE^{max} is its hydroxylic nature. It has already been pointed out that MFE^{max} is indeed very small in alcoholic solvent mixtures. In water-dioxane mixture, it increases. But in most cases, a small amount of impurity of water in an aprotic solvent mixture causes the MFE to decrease considerably. One of the speculations is that rapid making and breaking of H bonds cause spin relaxation caused by the motion of a magnetic nucleus. However, the MFE^{max} in CD_3OD is only marginally lower than that in CH_3OH . Another possibility is that the OH group provides a different type of cage which generates a barrier between CIP and SSIP^{8c}.

Effect of paramagnetic ions on the MFE^{13}

A paramagnetic ion may couple with any of the two ion-radicals in the RIP. A coupled system causes a precession of the angular momentum vectors around the resultant vector. If a paramagnetic ion is present in the neighbourhood of a RIP and preferentially couples with the radical of opposite charge, the relative orientation of the two spin vectors of the RIP could change (Fig. 6b). Indeed, it was observed by us that the MFE on exciplex luminescence decreases linearly with the concentration of lanthanum acetylacetonate. The quenching power is proportional to the spin-only moment of the Ln^{3+} ion, and not to its total momentum (Fig. 6a). In other words, the quenching power vs number of f -electrons curve is unimodal peaking at Gd, instead of the usual bimodal nature of the total magnetic moment vs number of f -electrons curve. This anomalous observation was explained by Basu *et al.*¹³ using a spin-exchange hamiltonian.

Other aspects of MFE on exciplex luminescence

Fig. 7a

Conformer-I

H-atom, bonded to the N-atom, is at the axial position to the saturated ring, and it is the less energetic conformer in the ground state.

Conformer-II

H-atom, bonded to the N-atom, is at the equatorial position to the saturated ring, and it is the higher energetic conformer in the ground state. In the excited state the relative energetic position of conformer-I and -II with respect to each other is reversed.

Other questions that have been addressed to by us are : (i) Can magnetic nuclei of the solvent influence the MFE on exciplex luminescence? (ii) Can non-magnetic ions influence the MFE on exciplex luminescence? (iii) Could back-electron transfer rate determine MFE? (iv) How does the MFE vary with time? (v) Does MFE depend on the orientation of the RP with respect to the field? (vi) Can a polymer linkage enhance the MFE? Lack of time would not allow us to go into these interesting aspects.

Conformational aspect of C-T excited states

Before concluding I would like to make a brief comment on another recent aspect of luminescent C-T complex. Twisted intramolecular CT state (TICT) is one aspect which has drawn considerable attention; whether intramolecular charge-transfer state is twisted or not is a matter of controversy. Spectroscopy of jet-cooled donor-acceptor-solvent complexes have led to elucidation of PES of exciplexes¹⁴. Recently, we have investigated a molecule 1,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline where the geometry of the CT state could be obtained from the ground state through puckering (Fig. 7a)¹⁵. Calculations show that the lone-pair in the ground state is in the equatorial position, and hence, the transition probability for an electron to jump from the N-atom to the benzene ring is small. A flipping of the N-atom across the average plane makes the lone-pair orbital axial in nature. This axial N lone-pair orbital has considerable overlap with the benzene π -orbital and consequently the electron transfer is easily accomplished. This molecule therefore exhibits a flipped intra-molecular charge transfer (FICT) emission in aprotic polar solvent (Fig. 7b). In the

Fig. 7b. Emission spectra of THIQ in different solvents : (a) cyclohexane, (b) diethylether, (c) THF and (d) acetonitrile at room temperature.

C-T state, the H-atom is in the equatorial position and thus avoids abstraction by the negatively charged phenyl radical. Thus, in contrast to other exciplexes of a secondary amine, it fluoresces. In protic polar solvents, however, the lone-pair is engaged in bond formation with solvent molecules and is not available for charge transfer, as a result, the C-T band decreases in intensity (Fig. 7c).

Fig. 7c. Variation of LE-state and CT-state emission band intensity in different proportion of ethanol/acetonitrile solvent mixtures. The direction of arrows indicates the trend of the emission intensity with increasing proportion of ethanol. The figure in inset is the emission band of THIQ in pure ethanol.

Concluding remarks

The charge-transfer nature of exciplex luminescence was speculated by Ghosh and others long back. The subject has attracted the attention of Indian scientists and many laboratories have made contributions in this area. Our own contribution has been in the area of magnetic field effect on exciplex luminescence. Here one observes a complex interplay of spin evolution and spatial evolution. The question of the geometry of the CT state is also intriguing and interesting. Recent experiments are directed towards the excited state PES of exciplex and the spin-dependent dynamics on this PES. However, a complete understanding has still illuded us due to the intrinsic complexity of the problem.

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